

A generic simulator for Edge Computing platforms

Elias Del-Pozo

Computer Science and Engineering Department
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Leganés, Spain
Email: edelpozo@inf.uc3m.es

Félix García-Carballeira

Computer Science and Engineering Department
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Leganés, Spain
Email: felix.garcia@uc3m.es

Abstract—During the last few years, Internet of Things systems are increasingly common and therefore have spread to the majority of users who have different types of physical devices, but it also happens in Cloud environments, where these types of devices are used to process information, at different levels, reducing the computational load that it would take to deal with all the data that the users send daily through the network. In order to develop, in an efficient way, these Cloud environments formed by different layers to increase the computational capacity, reduce the load and the waiting times for the execution of the processes, it is proposed to design a simulator called ENIGMA capable of allowing the users to define their own execution platform and application to be used in order to determine the viability and performance of the developed environments. This simulator has proven to be able to evaluate the same environments and cases as other existing simulators, such as IoTSim-Stream.

Keywords-component—Internet of Things, Cloud Computing, Fog Computing, Edge Computing, Cloud, Big Data, Simgrid

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the amount of information transferred through the network is growing, increasing the need to create infrastructures capable of maintaining or managing all the data generated and transferred through the Internet. This has led to an increase in the amount of data being generated over the last few years, reaching *Zettabytes* [1].

This is why the need to develop new paradigms that simplify and speed up the management of this data arises, such as Edge Computing [2] or Fog Computing [3] and even Mobile Edge Computing [4]. These paradigms have been evolving in recent years, making it easier for developers and programmers to generate computational environments capable of distributing the workload or reducing response times.

In addition, these paradigms are aimed at reducing the computational load of mobile devices, radio frequency devices (*RFID*) or even smartwatches. Thanks to these paradigms, larger scale infrastructures have also emerged, such as Smart Cities [5] or Smart Houses [6], providing the environment with greater interaction with users during their use.

However, creating this type of infrastructure entails a significant economic and structural investment, so it is necessary to have good planning and organization of the

environment to be designed and basic knowledge to determine the feasibility of implementing such a system. In order to carry out these tasks, it is necessary to use simulators capable of showing results on the possibility of developing this type of environment. These simulators are mostly part of a series of simulation tools that facilitate their development, such as *OMNeT++* [7] or *Simgrid* [8].

From these simulation tools, the aim is to develop a new simulator capable of providing information related to the performance shown by an infrastructure or cloud environment that is formed by a series of devices or sensors from IoT, as well as another group formed by data centres capable of computing and storing the data sent by these devices. In addition, the generation of these infrastructures would be generated based on a template that the user must fill in, thus facilitating the creation of the platform and application.

This document is organized as follows: Section II will show the state of the art where the technologies or paradigms used during the last years will be summarized, followed by Section III where the model proposed for the creation of this simulator will be detailed. Then, in Section IV, the evaluation platform will be shown where the developed simulator will be validated based on other existing ones. Finally, in Section V, some brief conclusions and future work on the work carried out will be given.

II. STATE OF THE ART

This section will explain different paradigms that have emerged in recent years capable of handling the data currently being transferred through the network. These paradigms allow the computation of heavy jobs or processes that are sent from users thanks to the distribution of load and storage of information. Also, we describe different simulation tools that help in the creation of simulators capable of providing developers with reliable statistics on the possibility of creating the designed architectures.

A. Internet of Things

Today, the vast majority of people in the world are surrounded by electronic devices, both large and small, that allow communication between various points in the world in real time. This paradigm called the Internet of

Things (IoT) [9] consists of many electronic elements, mostly small, distributed in many areas, and connected to the Internet. These devices can range from RFID sensors to household appliances such as refrigerators or washing machines, and as technology advances, costs are falling, and therefore more of these devices are in the homes of end users, causing an increased flow of information through the network.

More precisely, the IoT paradigm is an evolution of the Internet as it focuses on the selection, collection, and use of data remotely, allowing an improvement in the quality of life of users who focus on other more important jobs. To achieve this objective, it is necessary to make use of devices or sensors that are connected to the network and that collect information from the environment so that it can be processed in real time and offer information to the user about what is happening [10].

One of the most important characteristics of this paradigm is to design an environment made up of sensors or intelligent devices capable of collecting data from their area in order to create related information that will later be processed. The way the information is sent, the energy used for its processing, and the system's architecture must also be taken into account. In addition, it should be noted that this paradigm emerged from others already in existence, such as Bluetooth or WiFi, which has allowed it to be more relevant lately, although it is also necessary for the infrastructure to ensure the transmission of information since it is a very important aspect to protect the data of the users [10][11].

B. Edge Computing

The distributed paradigm that brings data processing and storage as close as possible to the sensors and intelligent devices, reducing the physical distance between both extremes and, therefore, the response time is reduced, the data computation increases, and the computational load of the infrastructure is reduced [12].

This paradigm would increase the efficiency of network and computing use in a cloud environment, reducing its load before reaching the endpoints of the data centers. However, not always be an option, having to look for other alternatives such as Fog Computing or Cloudlets [13], which are cloud data centers that allow the use of mobile applications or intensive use of resources for mobile devices.

Although it is proven that computing heavy and complex tasks in the cloud have proven to be efficient for data processing, it will not always be the best choice for tasks that require a very short response time [12].

The Figure 1 shows, in a simplified way, the conventional structure of text to cloud computing, where data producers continuously generate information that is sent to the Cloud

Fig. 1: Cloud Computing Paradigm

environment, while the consumers of that information request data from the cloud.

C. Fog Computing

The Fog Computer [14] is a paradigm similar to Edge Computing and uses Edge devices to perform significant computational load, storage, and communication between network endpoints, i.e. a paradigm where a number of electronic devices that communicate with each other, either wirelessly or over the network, cooperate with each other and perform computationally intensive operations.

This paradigm seems to be similar to the previous one, so that both deals with data processing and information transmission in their own components to reduce the computational load of data centers and increase the speed of response to users, but they have a clear difference. While in Edge Computing, the functionality is performed in devices associated with the devices that are near the sensors, in Fog computing, the information processing is performed in the devices that are connected to the LAN and are not so close physically to these elements.

Among the characteristics that make up the Fog Computing paradigm, which also make it an extension of the non-trivial Cloud environment and which follows the idea of Edge Computing, we can highlight [15]:

- Knowledge of device location and low latency.
- Geographical distribution. Fog Computing demands the use of a distributed computing deployment offering a high quality of information flow
- Environmental monitoring with large scale sensor networks
- Real-time interactions with Fog applications
- Heterogeneity of Fog devices, allowing different tasks to be performed in various environments

D. Simulation tools

In this section, it is intended to explain different types of tools aimed at simulating distributed applications in heterogeneous environments, such as Simgrid [8][16] and Omnet++ [7] [17].

Simgrid [18], is a set of distributed application simulation tools applied to heterogeneous distributed environments. It

Fig. 2: Cloudsim architecture [24]

also offers models and APIs ready to simulate distributed computing platforms and has been used, above all, to design simulators with good results in different fields such as, for example, Grid Computing [19], Cloud Computing [20], Volunteer Computing [21], among others.

On the other hand, there is OMNeT++ [17] which is a modular simulator of discrete network events that is used, mainly, to be able to model network protocols, multiprocessors and distributed systems, or any other system that can be simulated with discrete events. It provides a component architecture by model. That is, these models are formed by reusable components. These components can be connected to each other through different gates and combined to form composite modules [22].

E. Simulators

The following lines will explain the different simulators that currently exist and are widely used in Cloud environments. More specifically, those simulators whose objective is to give results on IoT [23], Edge Computing and Fog Computing infrastructures will be shown. Among the existing ones, Cloudsim [24] [25], IoTSim [26], IoTSim-Stream [27] and, finally, IoTNetSim [28] stand out.

1) *Cloudsim* [24]: Cloudsim is a simulator tool that enables the modelling and simulation of computer systems and Cloud applications. This simulator is divided into different layers to simulate virtual environments of data centers, as well as provides support in managing the interfaces of virtual machines, memory, storage or network bandwidth.

Figure 2 shows the layered architecture of the simulator, which is divided into several levels, offering the user the possibility of designing their own platforms, policies, or characteristics of the components that make up the simulator, in addition to the topology of the network and how to compute the work of the applications. It should also be noted that many other simulators have been developed from this one.

2) *IoTSim* [26]: IoTSim extends Cloudsim's design, based on the idea of layered architecture, adding support for Big Data processing frameworks. In addition, it is capable of simulating the processing of large amounts of data from IoT devices. It is characterized by different layers:

- **Cloudsim Core Simulation Engine Layer:** This is the deepest layer in the simulator. It offers support for event processing and service creation, virtual machines, among others.
- **Cloudsim's Simulation Layer:** Layer that offers simulation and modeling support in virtualized data center environments, in addition, to support for memory, storage, and bandwidth maintenance.
- **Storage Layer:** Layer that allows the modeling of different storage, such as HDFS or Azure Blob Storage, where the data generated by the applications will be stored while the simulation is running.
- **Processing Layer Big Data:** Formed by two sub-layers, it supports applications that need processing using MapReduce or a flow computing model depending on what is needed for its execution.
- **User Code Layer:** The most external layer that allows you to indicate the number of machines and their specifications, application configurations, etc. This layer helps the designer to create his own simulation scenarios.

3) *IoTSim-Stream* [27]: IoTSim-Stream arose from the need to develop workflow applications, so this simulator offers an environment capable of modeling complex flow chart applications in a Cloud infrastructure. Part of the code used in this simulator comes from Cloudsim.

More specifically, IoTSim-Stream is a simulator based on the data flow from directed acyclic graphs. That is, this simulator allows the design of IoT infrastructures from a graph where the amount of information that is received, processed, and sent to different nodes that make up the network is described through different parameters that model the simulation, the application and the user's requirements.

4) *IoTNetSim* [28]: IoTNetSim is another IoT simulator that has different layers for the simulation of IoT and network services. In addition, it has a multi-layer modular architecture so that it allows the design and development of different structures or IoT environments but what differentiates it from the rest is the fact that it supports the configuration of the IoT infrastructure network in a more precise way along with tools to support the mobility of the devices that make up the system.

Similar to the layered structure of the rest of the simulators, this simulator has the Fog Computing, Edge Computing, IoT, and application simulation layers, in addition to the Cloudsim own layers.

Fig. 3: ENIGMA Architecture

III. PROPOSED MODEL

This section will show different important elements that make up the developed ENIGMA simulator, such as the applications that can be designed, both data flow applications and those oriented to service processing, as well as the different components of the environment that make up the simulator.

A. Applications

In this simulator there are two well distinguished types of applications, data flow applications and applications oriented to the application or processing of services which will be explained in detail below.

1) *Data Flow Application:* Data flow applications are made up of data generated by IoT devices, sensors, or even mobile devices that are constantly sent over a period of time through the nodes that make up the platform's network. The information will have to be processed by each of the zones through which it passes, with a certain amount of processing required to be able to run it. The execution of this type of flow application is therefore continuous. Although Figure 4 only shows the possibility of sending replicas

between the different nodes that make up the platform, it is also possible to send part of this information, that is, to subdivide the computation of the information generated by the sensors, reducing the computational load of the system.

2) *Service Processing Application:* Similar to what happens with the previous applications, in the service processing applications, the information is passed to the Cloud environment in such a way that, once the information has been processed to the node, it has reached depending on the load distribution policy. A response will be sent to the device or sensor indicating that the count for that job has been completed. A simple example of how a job processing oriented application could be designed is shown in Figure 5.

However, it is also possible to add another processing layer, which can reduce the computational load of the environment, and which makes it possible to compute part of the information flow in mobile devices, since, during the last few years, these devices are capable of performing more expensive tasks and are increasingly powerful, in other words, this means talking about Mobile Edge Computing.

Fig. 4: Simple data flow application model

Fig. 5: Simple processing application model

B. Architecture

First, a spreadsheet will have to be completed that can be opened by tools such as Microsoft Excel or others, which will provide a template with different arguments that the user will have to complete.

There are two different parts, one part that would be specific to the IoT devices and another part that would allow defining the parameters that make up the server side, which in this case would be the nodes of a datacenter. Initially, the user can define both a group or cluster of IoT devices and a data center group formed by as many nodes as desired. In addition, the user will have to indicate the connections that make up the platform, that is, indicate the links between the different elements that make up the architecture to be simulated.

Fig. 6: Data flow from App 1

More specifically, this simulator is developed in C and uses the simulation tools offered by Simgrid, i.e. it uses the MSG API for sending and receiving data; the internal core of SimGrid called SURF; XBT which allows the simulator to use different types of data and finally TRACE, which is used to map the mechanisms used.

To explain the architecture of the simulator shown in Figure 3, the components are divided into two groups, server side and client side. On the server side there may be Edge Computing, Fog Computing and Cloud Computing layers, while the client side may be made up of different types of sensors or IoT devices.

IV. EVALUATION PLATFORM

In this section, the validation of the simulator and a performance study will be carried out to determine the feasibility of this project. In order to carry out the validation of the simulator, three applications have been designed based on the tests carried out for the validation of the IoTSim-Stream simulator in [27].

A. Simulator Validation

In order to carry out these tests, a number of considerations must be taken into account. First of all, the environment where the simulator has been developed has been in a laptop MSI GE60 2PE Apache Pro, with an i7-4720HQ processor, 8GB RAM, and 1TB SSD. In addition, for the correct execution of the processes received by each node of the applications, they make use of several virtual machines that are already explained in the mentioned article.

1) *Application 1:* In the first application, there are four nodes distributed in two different data centers that will process a certain amount of data per second. This data will be generated by a device called IoT0 that will generate every second 4 MB of data with a certain amount of counting necessary to perform it.

These data will be transferred for each node that will have an associated virtual machine, and, besides, it will have a computing power capable of processing this information. As shown in the figure, the network indicates that replicas of the data are being transferred as the simulation time increases.

Finally, after the execution of this application, the result is shown in Figure 7 which, as can be seen, the results are very similar to those obtained in the IoTSim-Stream simulator and

Fig. 7: Validation App 1

Fig. 8: Data flow from App 2

that obtained by the authors in a theoretical way (Real in the Figure).

2) *Application 2*: Similar to Application 1, there are four nodes divided into two different data centers that have the same characteristics as those defined for Application 1 except that nodes S0, S1, and S2 use a small virtual machine, while node S3 uses a medium virtual machine.

Furthermore, in this application, there is no sequential processing of the data that goes from one node to the next, but the S0 node will replicate twice the information it receives from the IoT0 device and then replicate the data in S1 and S2 that will finally be received by S3, as shown in Figure 8.

After executing Application 2 which follows the flow associated with Figure 8, it can be seen that the results are similar to those obtained with the IoTSim-Stream simulator and with the data to be obtained theoretically (Real), as shown below (Figure 9).

3) *Application 3*: Finally, Application 3 has a data flow structure as shown in Figure 10. After running the simulation, the results are shown in Figure 11, which also shows a similar amount of processed data per second as the simulation time progresses.

After analyzing the results obtained in the three applications, the amount of data processed during the simulation is similar with respect to the theoretically processed data and the data processed by the IoTSim-Stream simulator. These results allow

Fig. 9: Validation App 2

Fig. 10: Data flow from App 3

us to validate the results obtained by ENIGMA.

B. Simulator Performance

In this section, we use the simulator developed to analyze the performance and capabilities of an infrastructure formed by sensors in the Edge layer and nodes in the Fog layer. More specifically, a specific platform has been configured in order to obtain the amount of data processed in two layers, the Fog layer, and the Cloud layer. We also obtain the CPU usage and the power consumed in both layers, whose information

Fig. 11: Validation App 3

Fig. 12: Use case

is generated by a series of sensors located in the Edge layer.

We have an environment formed by a set of 10000 sensors that will produce data from time to time. Specifically, each sensor will send 1000 data of 4 KiB, half of them will send the information every second, and the other half every two seconds. This information needs a processing capacity equal to 1 GFLOP that will be sent at random and with a certain percentage of processing to the Fog layer. Once some of the data is processed in the Fog layer, it will be sent to the Cloud layer.

The results related to CPU usage are shown in Figure 13. As can be seen, although initially, the entire load lies in the Cloud layer, only 45% of the CPU is used on average between the 6 nodes which make up the layer, and its calculation is reduced by half if 90% is processed in the Fog layer.

Fig. 13: CPU usage

Another important element is the energy consumption that may be involved in implementing this architecture. To this end, the Simgrid tool collects, during the simulation, the actions performed by the components and, together with the energies that the user enters in the Excel file, ENIGMA is capable of generating a list with the energy consumed by each element, in Joules, at the end of the execution. Therefore, Figure 14 shows the average energy consumed both in the Fog layer formed by 10 nodes and the average energy consumed by the

6 nodes that make up the Cloud layer.

Fig. 14: Energy Consumption

As can be seen in the Figure 14, initially, the Cloud layer will consume around 12 MJ of energy on average, since it will process all the information generated by the sensors, while the Fog layer reaches 53 kJ of average consumption, a value that will increase as the amount of information processed in this layer increases. It is important to highlight the reduction of energy in the Cloud as it manages to reduce up to almost 10 times the original energy with a 90% of computation in the Fog. As can be seen, it is clear that a good simulation can provide data of great impact to implement these platforms by reducing energy consumption as much as possible.

Finally, another of the most important elements when performing simulations is the virtual memory used by the execution of the simulation in the computer or environment where it is performed. Specifically, for these tests, three different cases have been used where the difference lies in the number of sensors that are created before the simulation begins. In Table I three cases can be seen, one with 10,000 sensors, another with 100,000 sensors and finally another case with 1,000,000 sensors.

TABLE I: Virtual memory Usage

Number of Sensors	Virtual Memory Usage (GB)
10,000	78.16
100,000	783.36
1,000,000	7,833.6

As can be seen in Table I, as the number of sensors used increases every ten times, the use of virtual memory also increases by ten, so there is a linear relationship between memory and the number of components to use on a platform, so it follows that you can easily calculate the resources used if you increase or decrease the platform.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The simulator developed for this work offers the user the ability to generate their own environments or platforms through an Excel document where they can complete different fields that will be part of the components of the execution platform, both the client and the server part, along with the design of the application to be simulated, whether it is a service-oriented application or a data flow application. These features, offered by the simulator, would save monetary investments in infrastructures that could not be profitable, and, as the platform can be modified, it could show the scalability of the developed infrastructure. It can also offer the performance shown if aspects such as load balancing between the nodes or even the storage of information in certain nodes were taken into account.

There are several future lines of research in this field that could be further developed in future versions:

- To develop new types of platform that allow exploring other architectures of Cloud Computing to be able to make more evaluations oriented to its viability
- To offer users the possibility of using Mobile Edge Computing environments on the platform so that the sensors or IoT devices are capable of computing part of the information generated during the simulation
- Possibility of introducing load distribution and processing algorithms according to the computational load of the components of the server part, allowing the reduction of power consumption and CPU usage in those elements that are overloaded.
- Ability to introduce errors in the simulator to detect data transmission failures between components.

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